

A New Technique for Nonlinear Estimation

Curtis P. Mracek¹, James R. Cloutier², and Christopher A. D'Souza³

Navigation and Control Branch
U. S. Air Force Armament Directorate
Eglin AFB, Florida 32542-6810

Abstract

A new nonlinear filter referred to as the state-dependent Riccati equation filter (SDREF) is presented. The SDREF is derived by constructing the dual of a little known nonlinear regulator control design technique [1] which involves the solution of a state-dependent Riccati equation (SDRE) and which has been appropriately called the SDRE control method. The resulting SDREF has the same structure as the continuous steady-state linear Kalman filter. In contrast to the linearized Kalman filter (LKF) and the extended Kalman filter (EKF) which are based on linearization, the SDREF is based on a parameterization that brings the nonlinear system to a linear structure having state-dependent coefficients (SDC). In a deterministic setting, before stochastic uncertainties are introduced, the SDC parameterization fully captures the nonlinearities of the system. It was shown in [1] that, in the multivariable case, the SDC parameterization is not unique and that the SDC parameterization itself can be parameterized. This latter parameterization creates extra degrees of freedom that are not available in traditional filtering methods. These additional degrees of freedom can be used to either enhance filter performance, avoid singularities, or avoid loss of observability. The main intent of this paper is to introduce the new nonlinear filter and to illustrate the behavioral differences and similarities between the new filter, the LKF, and the EKF using a simple pendulum problem. The theoretical aspects of the filter are not presented here since they are yet to be investigated.

1. Introduction

The SDRE method is an emerging control design methodology. It represents a systematic way of de-

signing nonlinear feedback controllers for a broad class of nonlinear regulator problems. It has been used in [2] to produce advanced guidance algorithms, used in [3] and [4] for autopilot design, used in [5] for a nonlinear benchmark problem design and is briefly mentioned in [6]. The SDRE technique can be illustrated by considering the following nonlinear regulator problem:

Minimize

$$I = \frac{1}{2} \int_{t_0}^{\infty} x^T Q(x)x + u^T R(x)u dt \quad (1)$$

with respect to the state x and control u subject to the nonlinear differential constraint

$$\dot{x} = f(x) + g(x)u \quad (2)$$

where $x \in R^n$, $u \in R^m$, $f(x) \in C^\infty$, $g(x) \in C^\infty$, $Q(x) \in C^\infty$, $R(x) \in C^\infty$ and where $Q(x) = C^T(x)C(x) \geq 0$, and $R(x) > 0$ for all x . Here it is assumed that $f(0) = 0$ and $g(x) \neq 0$ for all $x \neq 0$. The SDRE approach for obtaining a suboptimal solution of Problem (1)-(2) is:

i) Use direct parameterization to bring the nonlinear dynamics to the state-dependent coefficient (SDC) form

$$\dot{x} = A(x)x + B(x)u \quad (3)$$

where

$$f(x) = A(x)x \quad B(x) = g(x) \quad (4)$$

ii) Solve the state-dependent Riccati equation (SDRE)

$$A^T(x)P + PA(x) - PB(x)R^{-1}(x)B^T(x)P + Q(x) = 0 \quad (5)$$

to obtain $P \geq 0$. Note that P is a function of x .

iii) Construct the nonlinear feedback controller via

$$u = -R^{-1}(x)B^T(x)P(x)x \quad (6)$$

The following interesting properties of the SDRE method are proven in [1]: a) In the case of scalar

¹Lt Col, USAF

²Senior Scientist

³Control Research Engineer

x , the SDRE method yields the optimal solution of the nonlinear regulator problem even when the state and control weighting matrices are functions of x . b) In the multivariable case, i) under mild conditions of stabilizability and detectability, the method is locally asymptotically stable, ii) with $\lambda = P(x)x$, the necessary condition for optimality $H_u = 0$ is always satisfied, iii) under stability, as the states are driven toward zero, with $\lambda = P(x)x$, the necessary condition for optimality $\dot{\lambda} = -H_x$ is asymptotically satisfied at a quadratic rate. Properties ii) and iii) represent a nice suboptimality property of the method and result in the SDRE control trajectories converging to the optimal control trajectories as the states are decreased. If the states are being effectively regulated and are being kept reasonably small, the suboptimality property can lead to near optimal nonlinear feedback control [1,5].

It was also shown in [1] that if $A_1(x)$ and $A_2(x)$ are distinct SDC parameterizations, then

$$A(x, \alpha) = \alpha A_1(x) + (1 - \alpha) A_2(x) \quad (7)$$

is also an SDC parameterization for any α . Note that $A(x, \alpha)$ represents an infinite family of SDC parameterizations contained in a line. In general, an SDC parameterization $A(x, \alpha)$ can be constructed which is the parametric representation of a hyperplane containing k distinct parameterizations (if they exist), where α is a vector of dimension $k - 1$. The introduction of α creates extra degrees of freedom that can be used not only to enhance the SDRE controller, but also its dual, the SDRE filter.

The positive characteristics of the SDRE control method motivated the development of the new nonlinear estimator which noteworthy has already been used successfully as an observer in [3]. In the next section, the SDREF is derived. In Section 3, the extra degrees of freedom that are available in the SDREF are discussed. In Section 4, the SDREF, the linearized Kalman filter (LKF) [7], and the extended Kalman filter (EKF) [8] are applied to a pendulum problem and compared. The paper is then concluded with a summary section.

2. The SDREF Derivation

Upon examining Eqs. (1)-(6), it can be seen that the time-invariant infinite-horizon nonlinear regulator problem being considered is a generalization of the time-invariant infinite-horizon linear-quadratic regulator problem where all of the coefficient matrices are state-dependent. When these coefficient matrices are constant, the nonlinear regulator problem collapses

to the linear regulator problem and the SDRE control method collapses to the steady-state linear regulator. We can obtain the filtering counterpart of the SDRE control algorithm by taking the dual of the steady-state linear regulator and then allowing the coefficient matrices of the dual to be state-dependent. The dual of the steady-state linear regulator is the steady-state continuous Kalman observer which in the absence of control reduces to the steady-state continuous Kalman filter. This leads to the following.

The SDC Form and the SDRE Filter

Consider the stochastic nonlinear system

$$\dot{x} = f(x) + \Gamma w \quad (8)$$

$$y = h(x) + v \quad (9)$$

where w is Gaussian zero-mean white process noise with $E[w(t)w^T(t + \tau)] = W(t)\delta(\tau)$ and v is Gaussian zero-mean white measurement noise with $E[v(t)v^T(t + \tau)] = V(t)\delta(\tau)$.

After bringing the system to the SDC form

$$\dot{x} = F(x)x + \Gamma w \quad (10)$$

$$y = H(x)x + v \quad (11)$$

the SDRE filter is given by

$$\dot{\hat{x}} = F(\hat{x})\hat{x} + K_f(\hat{x})[y(x) - H(\hat{x})\hat{x}] \quad (12)$$

where

$$K_f(\hat{x}) = PH^T(\hat{x})V^{-1} \quad (13)$$

and P is the positive definite solution to

$$F(\hat{x})P + PF^T(\hat{x}) - PH^T(\hat{x})V^{-1}H(\hat{x})P + \Gamma^T W \Gamma = 0 \quad (14)$$

3. Additional Degrees of Freedom

The additional degrees of freedom provide by the nonuniqueness of the SDC parameterization can be used to either enhance the filter's performance, avoid singularities, or avoid loss of observability. In this section we show with a single extra degree of freedom how we can avoid loss of observability in a simple example problem. Consider the system with dynamics

$$\dot{x}_1 = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = 0 \quad (16)$$

where $x_1(0)$ and $x_2(0)$ are zero-mean Gaussian-distributed random variables and where the measurement equations are given by

$$y_1 = h_1(x) = x_1 + x_2 + v_1 \quad (17)$$

$$y_2 = h_2(x) = x_1 x_2 + v_2 \quad (18)$$

with v_1 and v_2 representing white measurement noise processes. In the EKF, the nonlinear observation function $h(x)$ has to be linearized about \hat{x} for use in the gain and covariance computations (see Eqs. (40)-(42)). This yields

$$H(\hat{x}) \triangleq \frac{\partial h(\hat{x})}{\partial x} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ \hat{x}_2 & \hat{x}_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

For the SDREF, there exist two distinct SDC parameterizations:

$$H_1(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & x_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad H_2(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ x_2 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

which lead to the parameterized SDREF measurement coefficient matrix

$$H(\hat{x}, \alpha) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ \alpha \hat{x}_2 & (1 - \alpha) \hat{x}_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

Note that for the EKF, $H(\hat{x})$ loses rank whenever $\hat{x}_1 = \hat{x}_2$ and there is nothing that can be done about it. For the SDREF, $H(\hat{x}, \alpha)$ loses rank whenever $(1 - \alpha)\hat{x}_1 = \alpha\hat{x}_2$ but α can be selected (or changed in value) to prevent this from happening. Thus, for this example, loss of observability can be avoided in the SDREF except for the trivial case $\hat{x}_1 = \hat{x}_2 = 0$.

4. Simple Pendulum Problem

The new SDREF will now be applied to a simple two dimensional pendulum problem and compared with the linearized Kalman filter (LKF) and the EKF. The pendulum model has two state variables, $x = [\theta, \dot{\theta}]^T$, where θ and $\dot{\theta}$ are the angular position and angular rate of the pendulum. The equations of motion are given by

$$\dot{x}_1 = x_2 \quad (22)$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = -\frac{g}{L} \sin(x_1) \quad (23)$$

The measurement is from an accelerometer attached to the bob of the pendulum. Thus the measurement equation is

$$y = -\frac{g}{L} \sin(x_1) \quad (24)$$

The parameterization chosen for the SDREF is

$$F(\hat{x}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -\frac{g}{L} \frac{\sin(\hat{x}_1)}{\hat{x}_1} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

$$H(\hat{x}) = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{g}{L} \frac{\sin(\hat{x}_1)}{\hat{x}_1} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

Since this is a simple problem the closed form solution can be obtained by solving the state dependent Riccati equation analytically. This leads to the SDREF

gain of

$$K_f = \begin{bmatrix} -\sqrt{\frac{L\hat{x}_1}{g \sin(\hat{x}_1)}} \sqrt{-2 + 2\sqrt{1 + \frac{G_{22}}{V}} + \frac{G_{11}}{V} \frac{\sin(\hat{x}_1)}{L\hat{x}_1}} \\ 1 - \sqrt{1 + \frac{G_{22}}{V}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (27)$$

and the SDREF filter equations

$$\dot{\hat{x}}_1 = \frac{-(y - \hat{y})L\hat{x}_1}{g \sin(\hat{x}_1)} \phi(\hat{x}_1) + \hat{x}_2 \quad (28)$$

$$\dot{\hat{x}}_2 = (y - \hat{y}) \left(1 - \sqrt{1 + \frac{G_{22}}{V}} \right) - \frac{g}{L} \sin(\hat{x}_1) \quad (29)$$

where

$$\phi(\hat{x}_1) = \sqrt{-2 + 2\sqrt{1 + \frac{G_{22}}{V}} + \frac{G_{11}}{V} \frac{g \sin(\hat{x}_1)}{L\hat{x}_1}} \quad (30)$$

and

$$\hat{y} = -\frac{g}{L} \sin(\hat{x}_1) \quad (31)$$

where

$$\Gamma^T W \Gamma = \begin{bmatrix} G_{11} & 0 \\ 0 & G_{22} \end{bmatrix} \quad (32)$$

Note that for $\hat{x}_1 = \pi$ radians there is a singularity in the SDREF gain. This can possibly be overcome by parameterizing the SDC parameterization in terms of α (based on a second distinct parameterization) and selecting α so that the singularity is avoided. This would allow the SDREF to track the pendulum through 360 degrees. This will be investigated and included in a future draft of the paper.

The LKF is based on the linearization of the pendulum problem about the nominal trajectory $x_1(t) = 0$, $x_2(t) = 0$. The coefficient matrices for the linearized model are

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -\frac{g}{L} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{g}{L} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (34)$$

The LKF gain is given by

$$K_f = \begin{bmatrix} -\sqrt{\frac{L}{g}} \sqrt{-2 + 2\sqrt{1 + \frac{G_{22}}{V}} + \frac{G_{11}}{V} \frac{g}{L}} \\ 1 - \sqrt{1 + \frac{G_{22}}{V}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (35)$$

and the LKF equations are

$$\dot{\hat{x}}_1 = \frac{-(y - \hat{y})L}{g} \psi + \hat{x}_2 \quad (36)$$

$$\dot{\hat{x}}_2 = (y - \hat{y}) \left(1 - \sqrt{1 + \frac{G_{22}}{V}} \right) - \frac{g}{L} \hat{x}_1 \quad (37)$$

where

$$\psi = \sqrt{-2 + 2\sqrt{1 + \frac{G_{22}}{V}} + \frac{G_{11}}{V} \frac{g}{L}} \quad (38)$$

and

$$\hat{y} = -\frac{g}{L}\hat{x}_1 \quad (39)$$

It should be noted that neither the SDREF nor the LKF requires integration of the covariance matrix, only the integration of the state equations.

The continuous time-invariant EKF is defined by the propagation equations

$$\dot{\hat{x}} = f(\hat{x}) + PH^T V^{-1} [y - h(\hat{x})] \quad (40)$$

$$\dot{P} = FP + PF^T - PH^T V^{-1} HP + \Gamma^T W \Gamma \quad (41)$$

where

$$F = \frac{\partial f(\hat{x})}{\partial x} \quad H = \frac{\partial h(\hat{x})}{\partial x} \quad (42)$$

For the pendulum problem, the EKF equations are given by

$$\dot{\hat{x}}_1 = \hat{x}_2 - \frac{g}{L} \cos(\hat{x}_1)(y - \hat{y})P_{11}V^{-1} \quad (43)$$

$$\dot{\hat{x}}_2 = -\frac{g}{L} \sin(\hat{x}_1) - \frac{g}{L} \cos(\hat{x}_1)(y - \hat{y})P_{12}V^{-1} \quad (44)$$

where

$$\hat{y} = -\frac{g}{L} \sin(\hat{x}_1) \quad (45)$$

and

$$\dot{P}_{11} = 2P_{12} - \frac{g^2}{L^2} P_{11}^2 \cos^2(\hat{x}_1)V + G_{11} \quad (46)$$

$$\dot{P}_{12} = P_{22} - \frac{g}{L} \cos(\hat{x}_1) - \frac{g^2}{L^2} P_{11}P_{12} \cos^2(\hat{x}_1)V \quad (47)$$

$$\dot{P}_{22} = -2P_{12} \frac{g}{L} \cos(\hat{x}_1) - \frac{g^2}{L^2} P_{12}^2 \cos^2(\hat{x}_1)V + G_{22} \quad (48)$$

5. Numerical Results

All simulation results were determined using Matlab and Simulink. The program was run using $g = 32.2 \frac{\text{ft}}{\text{sec}^2}$ and $L = 1$ ft. The numerical integration was performed using a fourth order Runge-Kutta scheme with a fixed step size of $dt = 0.005$ sec. A measurement noise intensity of $V = 2$ was used for all of the filters. The process noise intensity was selected to be $G_{11} = 0.05$ and $G_{22} = 0.05$.

Two numerical experiments are presented using the three filters. In the first experiment, the initial conditions input into the filter are the same as the actual initial position ($x_1 = 1$ rad and $x_2 = 0$ rad/sec). Figures 1 through 4 show the results. Figure 1 has the three filter outputs for x_1 , the pendulum position. Figure 2 illustrates the error in the position estimate. Note how similar the SDREF is to the EKF. Figure 3 presents the the estimated rate x_2 for the three filters. Figure 4 is the rate errors. Notice how both

the SDREF and the EKF provide nonlinear estimates whereas the LKF, because it is a linear filter, cannot capture the nonlinearities and thus produces a phase shift and amplitude scaling.

In the second numerical experiment, the filters' initial conditions did not coincide with the actual initial conditions. The results of this experiment are presented in Figures 5 through 8. The same information and ordering are used in these figures. As can be seen the SDREF and the LKF have very similar growth characteristics, while the EKF does not. The initial values of the covariance matrix for the EKF were set to zero, indicating perfect knowledge of the initial states.

Figure 1: Position Estimates Same Initial Condition

Figure 2: Position Errors Same Initial Condition

Figure 3: Rate Estimates Same Initial Condition

Figure 6: Position Errors Different Initial Condition

Figure 4: Rate Errors Same Initial Condition

Figure 7: Rate Estimates Different Initial Condition

Figure 5: Position Estimate Different Initial Condition

Figure 8: Rate Errors Different Initial Condition

6. Summary

A new nonlinear filtering technique has been developed and demonstrated. The new filter is based on a parameterization of the nonlinear dynamics and nonlinear measurements which gives rise to a linear structure having state-dependent coefficients. The SDRE filter represents the "dual" of the SDRE control algorithm which is proving to be highly effective in solving nonlinear regulator problems. A numerical experiment was conducted using a simple pendulum operating in the nonlinear regime. For this example, the results show that the SDREF has the same characteristics as the EKF but does not require propagation of the covariance matrix. It was also shown that the new filter has the same nominal growth characteristics as the LKF when the initial state estimates are different than the actual initial values. Future work on the filter will include investigating the theoretical properties of the algorithm, both as an observer and as a filter.

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